

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON THE USAGE OF ENDEARMENT UNITS BETWEEN GENDER

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ABSTRACT

Thus, there was a concept "gender" meaning set of social and cultural norms which society orders to carry out to people depending on their biological floor. This article illustrates several endearing words used in Uzbek and English and compares some differences and similarities in the usage of these units between gender.

Keywords: Gender, analysis, language, speech, endearment words, affection, caressing suffixes, subjective assessment.

INTRODUCTION

For the first time the floor factor in connection with language arose in antiquity at judgment of category of a grammatical gender. The most ancient and long time the only hypothesis of the reasons of emergence and functioning in language of category of a sort became symbolic and semantic, being based on correlation of natural biological category sexus from grammatical genus. Supporters of this hypothesis considered that the grammatical gender arose under the influence of a natural reality – presence of people of a different floor (Herder, Humboldt, Grimm, etc.) at the same time researchers made use of the not language experience for an explanation of extralinguistic motivation of category of a sort. It led to emergence of estimation in interpretation of category of a sort: the masculine gender appeared to the names, paramount because of attributing, relating to it, semantics of force, activity, energy.

Names of a feminine gender, on the contrary, were characterized by passivity, subordination. Thus, conditions of social reality were extrapolated to laws of development of language that is confirmed by basic gender researches E. Borneman, where the analysis is kept in terms of cross-disciplinary approach. The blow to a symbolic and semantic hypothesis was struck by opening of languages in which the

category of a sort is absent. When studying a gender factor in language – many linguists –of the Russian school which declared in the late eighties (Haleeva I.I., Kirilina A.V., Malishevskoy D.Ch., etc.) is called the linguoculturological approach assuming studying of courage and femininity as basic cultural concepts.

The public importance of category "gender" justifies its application to all language phenomena concerning floor problems. "A floor and its manifestations not just "are registered" language, but get an axiology, are estimated in terms of a naive picture of the world.

Researches of the 1970th differ in a depopulation of the conclusions which are contained in them that demonstrates "recognition" of a problem linguistic science. The theory of opposition of "women's cooperation" to "men's rivalry" in linguistic (speech) behavior became one of aspects of gender linguistics. Dale Spender ("The language created by the man", Spender, 1986) claims that in essence language is initially predisposed to establishment of superiority of men in society. This statement provoked a rough discussion on a problem: whether really the similar phenomena are caused by the fact that language creates reality, or words which people have at the order are irrelevant to thought processes.

In the course of knowledge from the world around objects, properties, processes not only real, but also inner worlds are isolated and called. It is possible to carry images, symbols, standards and stereotypes of culture to the last and also recognized as society of value ethical standards. The gender stereotypes arising over biologically - sexual reality, reflect the set of biological signs, social roles, features of mentality and behavior inherent in representatives of this floor within this culture.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Terms such as a masculinity and a femininity in relation to gender stereotypes, representing as conceptual metaphors (P. Lakoff) transfer internally contradictory and at the same time, dynamic ratio of men's and women's substrates. [4 with 45-49] Manifestations of a masculinity and femininity can be observed in the most different spheres, for example, in behavior types, in different types of social activity and also in the language describing these phenomena.

Turning into results of the dictionary analysis, the analysis of the British dictionaries of the middle of the XX century illustrates the provision of feministic linguistics that lexicographic sources reflect and reproduce the sexist use of language. The research was conducted on material of the illustrative contexts (IC) of the "Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English" A.S.Hornby dictionary, [5,with 112-118] authoritative

in the 1940-50th years, prod. 1942, 1948, 1958 (ALDCE), also aimed to track as in this source are shown:

- obscurity of women in language;
- secondary position of the female status in relation to men's;
- stereotypical representation of both sexes, leading to
- in other words, how in dictionary entries the gender asymmetry is shown.

Lakoff (1975) pointed out that compared with men, women are more likely to use an interrogative sentence to express their idea, and they like to use tag questions, because tag questions can make the tone less tense. [11, with 78-80] Fishman (1980) collected many couples' conversation tapes, and he found that women used three times of tag questions as men did. In these conversations, they were 370 interrogative sentences, among which women used 263, almost two and a half of times of men did. This point is similar to the difference in intonation between men and women. Just as Lakoff (1975) said that women might answer a question with rising tone, while men like to use falling tone to make a firm statement. According to Lakoff (1975), women tend to do this because they are less sure about themselves and their opinions than men.

Context and function, rather than semantic or formal properties, have an influence on the usage of endearing words [6]. Although they have some conventionalization, the speaker's imagination and linguistic originality also matter. Accordingly, Z. Griffin [7] claims that fondness phrases are not necessarily indicative of the traits of the addressee. Accordingly, the speaker may choose to use honey, honey bunny, love, sweetie, etc. For instance, when used to address both men and women in a casual, relaxed setting, the word "mate" is seen as a friendly term or an affection.[8]

RESULTS

Swear words and Expletives Maybe because women are gentle and docile, they usually avoid using swear words and dirty words. They believe that these kinds of words will not only make others uncomfortable and give an impression of "no civilization", but also destroy the relationship between her and others. Women always pay more attention to the grace of themselves and their use of language. We rarely hear that women utter such words like "damn, fuck you, hell," instead they use "oh, dear, my god" to express their feelings. Diminutives Women like to use words that have the meaning of "small", such as bookie, hanky, panties. They also like to use words that show affections, such as dear, sweetie. Furthermore, women like to use words that show politeness, such as please, thanks, and they use more euphemism, but "slang" is considered to be men's preference. From the study we can see that men and women have their own vocabulary choices in achieving emphatic effects.

We often hear a woman says “well, you know..., I think..., I suppose....kind of, maybe I am wrong but..., etc. When they want to get help from others, men and women express their feeling in different ways as the following: Women: I was wondering if you can help me. Men: please give me a hand. From the above examples, we can see men tend to ask something directly, while women tend to be more polite.

b. Interrogative sentences Women use more interrogative sentences than men do. Women look interrogative sentences as a strategy of continuing a good conversation.

While there are several subjective evaluation forms such as -cha, -chak, -gina, -loq, -khan, -toy, -oy, -bibi, -chik, -boy, bek, -poshsha, -mirza, -bonu, -beka, -im in Uzbek, -king, -les, -ling, -cy, -sy, -ie, -y, -ey, -o are diminutive affixes in English. In English and in Uzbek, caressing suffixes are mainly added to nouns (kelin+poshsha, son+y) and adjectives (asal+cha+m, sweet+ie) and indicate the subjective attitude of the subject to the thing or concept represented by these words and creates a positive or negative stylistic color in these words. English cannot add more than two suffixes to a word (aunt+y, aunt+ie). In Uzbek, you can add several endearing suffixes to one word (qiz+cha, qiz +loq, qiz +gina+m). If in English only one caressing suffix is applied to one word (girl+ie), in Uzbek we can use two or more suffixes in a row (amma+jon+gina+m).

Pronouns also have an incomparable role in expressing the meaning of caressing. For example, in the Uzbek language, the first person reflexive pronoun “o‘zimning” and the personal pronoun “mening”, the possessive suffix -im serves to strengthen the meaning of caress (o‘zimning qizalog‘im, mening farishtam). In the Uzbek language, the suffixes -m, -im in the first person singular also express the meaning of caressing (bolajon+im), in English, the meaning of caressing is understood by putting the personal pronoun my before the word (my honey). The meaning of caressing can be represented not only with suffixes, but also with simple words (toy, sugar). In addition, we can express our love by saying the words in a soft, loving tone. That is why the most important tools in enhancing the meaning of caress are tone, intonation and beat. When petting young children, some sounds are dropped in English (sugar - suga, darling - darlin), and in Uzbek, consonants are changed and pronounced (shirinim - silinim, shakarim - shakayim) [5].

DISCUSSION

Context and function, rather than semantic or formal properties, have an influence on the usage of endearing words [6]. Although they have some conventionalization, the speaker’s imagination and linguistic originality also matter. Accordingly, Z. Griffin [7] claims that fondness phrases are not necessarily indicative of the traits of the

addressee. Accordingly, the speaker may choose to use honey, honey bunny, love, sweetie, etc. For instance, when used to address both men and women in a casual, relaxed setting, the word "mate" is seen as a friendly term or an affection.[8]

Social factors, such as gender and social status of a speaker and an addressee may play a crucial role in the choice of an endearment term when it comes to addressing those who are not sexually or emotionally intimate. The most common English endearment words are as follows:

Baby. Calling someone with the word "baby" is a common way to address a romantic partner (male or female). It would be weird if you said it to someone you are not in a relationship with. Sometimes, this affection word is applied in a short way as "babe". However, "babe" is also a slang term for an attractive woman. In Uzbek, the word is often utilized in its own sense, referring to a person who has just been born. Nevertheless, when the word is used in a figurative sense, it can be interpreted as a joke, a laugh, or a mockery among the subconscious [9].

Sweetheart. A very affectionate term for a loved one or romantic partner. "Sweetie" is also common. It is common in Uzbek too, with many pictures between the two lovers. However, the word sweet, like the words sweetheart, honey above, can also interact between our women and girls. In doing so, they can express feelings such as caressing each other, liking each other.

Sugar. Another term of endearment carries the meaning of sweetness. As we see, this is a common theme in terms of endearment around the world. The word "sugar" is commonly used between family members, between close female friends, when older people address kids and so on in the Uzbek language.

Dude. "Dude" is an American word that is getting more and more commonplace in English speaking countries all around the world. You can use it to address your male friends. In Uzbek, it means "oshna, og'ayni" and is used in the same way. Some people also utilize it to address women, although this is less common.

CONCLUSION

Briefly, there are both similarities and contrasts between the two language systems through our contrastive research, which also shown endearment terms are a social construction based on situational and cultural expectations, as well. At the same time, addressing to a male, friends, family members differentiate in cultural, traditional, linguistic sides in different languages, particularly Uzbek and English.

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